

ORANCHADA

Widget usage examples

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General recommendations

We recommend using a portable version of Orange analytics platform. The latter is a must, especially if Oranchada widgets are intended to be combined with Spectroscopy widgets.

This guide is tested with Orange version 3.37.0 and Oranchada add-on ver. 1.0.0

The orange portable version could be downloaded from:

<https://orangedatamining.com/download/>

or, if needed, from the download archive available at bottom of the page

Download archive

Download older versions from [our archive](#).

[Orange3-3.37.0-Python3.10.11-x86_64.dmg](#)

[Orange3-3.37.0-Python3.11.8-arm64.dmg](#)

[Orange3-3.37.0-Python311-win_amd64.exe](#)

[Orange3-3.37.0.zip](#)

[bkechem-0.12.0.tar.gz](#)

[buildC45.zip](#)

Orange 3.37.0 for Windows

Windows

Standalone installer (default)

[↓ Orange3-3.37.0-Miniconda-x86_64.exe](#)

Can be used without administrative privileges.

Recommended

Portable Orange

[↓ Orange3-3.37.0.zip](#)

No installation needed. Just extract the archive a

Starting the program Orange

"Welcome to Orange" shows some important basic functions: create a new project, open an existing one, or choose from the ones we recently worked on. There are also links to helpful information on how to work with Orange.

After successful installation of **Oranchada** add-on, you should see a set of widgets in two sub-sections: **Pro** and **Easy**

On the left you can see the main set of Oranchada Pro widgets:

Add Baseline, Add Noise, Add, Subtract, Baseline remove, Crop spectrum, Find Peaks, Fit Peaks, Gen Spectra, HDR Merger, HHT Sharpening, Load File, Load Test Spectra, Merger, Metadata editor, Moving minimum, Normalize, RS to WL, Recover Spikes, Resample NUDFT, Resample, Save spectra, Select, Set X-axis, Smooth spectrum, Edit Y Calibration Certificate, WL to RS, Xaxis fine calibration and Load File Names.

Oranchada add-on, **Easy** widgets

Oranchada Easy sub-section

x-calibration Apply

x-calibration Load

Get Noisy Spectra

CHARISMA database import

CHARISMA Twinning protocol

Table to RC Spectra

CHARISMA X axis calibration

Y axis calibration

Basic structure of all widgets

Widget options and settings

Resulting plot spectra

Widget input

Widget output

Main options:

Auto update plot - Settings modification triggers plot update

Pass datatable - Generate output compatible with widgets other than oranchada

Auto process - Settings modification triggers auto preprocessing

Preprocessing settings:

specific settings according to widget functionality

When mouse is over a widget, Orange shows a tip with the input and output widget channels

For example, the “HHT Sharpening” widget **Input** channel is “RC2Spectra” and respectively **Output** channels are “RC2Spectra” and “Data”.

Multiple channels widget

When connecting a widget to another multiple channels widget, as in the example workflow, we will get the following window asking users for information which channels to connect

1. Load a test spectrum

Click on the “Load Test Spectra” widget (or drag and drop) to put it on the main area of the Orange workflow

2. Zoom-in spectra (inspect a specific region)

3. Load a file

Load File - Orange

View Window Help

Main Options

- Auto update plot
- Pass datatable
- Auto process

Process

Plot

Plot legend

Load File

Load File

File format

Auto

Select a file from a user specified path

Open spectra

<< altered-to-be-used > ICV-iRaman-532

Search ICV-iRaman-532

Organize New folder

Name	Date modified	Type	Size
nCAL02_iRPlus532_Z020_100_2000ms.txt	5/18/2023 11:15 AM	Text Document	196
Ne_532nm_x20_5ms.txt	5/18/2023 11:15 AM	Text Document	189
Ne_532nm_x20_400ms.txt	5/18/2023 11:15 AM	Text Document	191
PST02_iRPlus532_Z020_100_550msx5.txt	5/18/2023 11:15 AM	Text Document	193
S0B02_iRPlus532_Z020_100_30000msx2.txt	5/18/2023 11:15 AM	Text Document	197
sCAL02_iRPlus532_Z020_100_3800ms.txt	5/18/2023 11:15 AM	Text Document	194

File name: PST02_iRPlus532_Z020_100_550msx5.txt

All spectra formats (*.txt *.csv)

Open Cancel

Main Options

- Auto update plot
- Pass datatable
- Auto process

Process

Plot

- Plot legend

Load File

Load File

File format

Auto

Click on "Plot" to visualize the spectrum loaded from file

4. Generate synthetic spectra with Gen Spectra widget

Main Options

- Auto update plot
- Pass datatable
- Auto process

Process

Plot

Plot legend

Gen Spectra

Spe Params

xmin: 2

xmax: 2000

n_bins: 1500

Deltas: 9, 2904.5: 13, 3054.3: 32

PST

Number of spectra: 1

x=1447. y=21.03

Specify "deltas" - peak positions by x-axis and the relative intensity of each peak.

If selected, this option will load Polystyrene spectrum default parameters

Set the number of spectra copies to be included.

5. Add Baseline and Noise to synthetic spectra

Set the parameters to add the baseline

Set the level of noise to be added to the spectrum

Workflow: Gen Spectra → RC2Spectra → Add Baseline → RC2Spectra → Add Noise

The 'Add Baseline' widget parameters are: num freq: 15, amplitude: 2.00000, intercept: 10.00000, slope: 0.01000, quadratic: -0.0000050.

The 'Add Noise' widget parameter is: Add Noise: 0.01000.

6. Generate synthetic Spectra with added Baseline and Noise

Generate synthetic spectra with Baseline and Noise with one widget from "Oranchada Easy" Category

7. Find peaks

Find Peaks - Orange

Main Options

- Auto update plot
- Pass datatable
- Auto process

Process

Plot

- Plot legend

Find Peaks

HTT Chain

80 20

Enable shaprening

Prominence [$\times\sigma$] 5.00

Window length 100

Min peak width 3

Minimum required intensity

Number of samples limiting the estimated area for each peak

Minimum required width

Resulting output table

1 RC2Spectra

Data: 1 instance, 2048 variables									
Features: 2048 numeric (no missing values)									
1	34	-45.87	-42.81	-39.75	-36.68	-33.62	-30.56	-27.51	-24.4

Main Options

- Auto update plot
- Pass datatable
- Auto process

- Plot legend

Find Peaks

HHT Chain

80 50

- Enable shaprening

Prominence [$\times\sigma$] 5.00

Window length 100

Min peak width 3

8. Fit peaks - can be placed only after Find peaks widget

Data: 1 instance, 2048 variables
Features: 2048 numeric (no missing values)

		-45.87	-42.81	-39.75	-36.68	-33.62	-30.56	-27.51	-24.4
1	34	82	124	-16	-44	-40	50	77	

Peaks: 13 instances, 12 variables
Features: 11 (1 categorical, 10 numeric) (no missing values)
Metas: string

y	index	amplitude	amplitude_stderr	center	center_stderr	sigma	sigma_stderr	
9	g00_p0	51500.5	1555.20	1448.26	0.215104	1.50411	0.227042	17.541
10	g07_p0	51463.4	3732.74	1583.28	0.343404	4.47518	0.364126	10.081
11	g07_p1	162470	3997.22	1602.37	0.137185	5.25565	0.14771	12.376
12	g08_p0	217611	13028	2906.72	0.873918	18.0356	0.989434	42.470
13	g09_p0	426828	11784.8	3054.81	0.284542	11.881	0.314323	27.977

Resulting output table with calculated parameters for fitted peaks indexed based on each specific peak group

9. RS to WL - Raman shift to Wavelength

The reverse functionality in:
“WL to RS” widget
(Wavelength to Raman shift)

10. Merger

The control panel for the 'Merger - Orange' widget. It includes a title bar, navigation icons (home, back, forward, zoom, search, and list), and a 'Main Options' section with the following settings:

- Auto update plot
- Pass datatable
- Auto process

A 'Process' button is located below the options.

The resulting spectrum is merged from the input spectra and each spectrum is shown in a different color

11. Normalize

12. Crop spectrum

13. Moving minimum (estimates baseline via moving minimum)

14. Subtract

Difference = Minuend - Subtrahend

Minuend a quantity or number from which another is to be subtracted

Subtrahend

The two spectra need to be with equal length and same x-axis

15. Resample NUDFT (Non-Uniform Discrete Fourier Transform)

Resample NUDFT (1) - Orange

Main Options

- Auto update plot
- Base datatable
- Auto process

Process

Plot

Plot legend

Resample NUDFT

x-min 0

x-max 3000

n-bins 3000

window

- bartlett
- barthann
- bartlett
- blackman
- blackmanharris
- bohman
- boxcar
- hamming
- hann
- nuttall
- parzen

Set the Resample parameters:
x-min - min value of new x-axis
x-max - max value of new x-axis
n-bins - number of bins

Select window function

HHT Sharpening (Hilbert - Huang Transform)

Screenshot of the Orange software interface showing the HHT Sharpening widget. The widget is titled "HHT Sharpening - Orange". The main options are:

- Auto update plot
- Pass datatable
- Auto process
- Process
- Plot
- Plot legend

The HHT Sharpening parameter is set to 800, which is highlighted with a red box. A red arrow points from this box to the right plot, with the text "Set window width of the moving minimum filter".

The right plot shows the result of the HHT Sharpening process. The x-axis ranges from 0 to 3000, and the y-axis ranges from 0 to 35000. The plot shows a much smoother baseline compared to the original spectrum, with the sharp peaks still visible. The legend indicates the data is from 'id(spe)=2776293211968'.

HDR Merge

16. Example with basic workflow for x calibration

Example workflow is available at:

<https://github.com/h2020charisma/oranchada/tree/main/examples>

Load PST with Load Test Spectra widget

Load Neon and Silicon spectra with Load Test Spectra

Widget

Use two separate widgets for Neon and Silicon, respectively

The example workflow uses **Load Test Spectra** widget.
In order to use your own spectra use **Load File** widget.

Crop spectra

e.g. Si spectrum is cropped in the interval [480, 600] cm⁻¹

id(spe)=2550950244432

50000
40000
30000
20000
10000
0

480 500 520 540 560 580 600

Raman shift [cm⁻¹]

50000
40000
30000
20000
10000
0

0 250 500 750 1000 1250 1500 1750 2000

Raman shift [cm⁻¹]

Baseline removal for the Si spectrum

Normalize Neon and Si spectra

Add and connect CHARISMA x axis calibration widget

This screenshot shows the 'Edit Links - Orange' dialog for the 'Load Test Spectra (PST)' widget. On the left, the widget's input is 'RC2Spectra' with an unchecked checkbox. On the right, the 'X axis calibration' widget is shown with three checkboxes: 'RC2Spectra' (checked), 'Neon spectrum' (unchecked), and 'Si spectrum' (unchecked). A red arrow points from the 'RC2Spectra' input of the 'Load Test Spectra (PST)' widget to the checked 'RC2Spectra' checkbox in the 'X axis calibration' widget.

This screenshot shows the 'Edit Links - Orange' dialog for the 'Normalize' widget. On the left, the widget's input is 'RC2Spectra' with an unchecked checkbox. On the right, the 'X axis calibration' widget is shown with three checkboxes: 'RC2Spectra' (unchecked), 'Neon spectrum' (checked), and 'Si spectrum' (unchecked). A red arrow points from the 'RC2Spectra' input of the 'Normalize' widget to the checked 'Neon spectrum' checkbox in the 'X axis calibration' widget.

This screenshot shows the 'Edit Links - Orange' dialog for the 'Normalize Si' widget. On the left, the widget's input is 'RC2Spectra' with an unchecked checkbox. On the right, the 'X axis calibration' widget is shown with three checkboxes: 'RC2Spectra' (unchecked), 'Neon spectrum' (unchecked), and 'Si spectrum' (checked). A red arrow points from the 'RC2Spectra' input of the 'Normalize Si' widget to the checked 'Si spectrum' checkbox in the 'X axis calibration' widget.

Each widget input must be connected with the proper widget output from the workflow

Setup CHARISMA x axis calibration widget

The screenshot shows the CHARISMA X axis calibration widget interface. On the left is a control panel with several sections: 'Main Options' (Auto update plot, Pass datatable, Auto process), 'CHARISMA X axis calibration' (Laser Wavelength [nm] set to 532), 'Peak profile' (Gaussian selected, Should fit checked), 'Lazer zeroing' (Pearson4 selected, Should fit checked), and 'Peak finding options' (prominence 3.0, wlen 200, width 1.0). A 'Save calibration model' button is at the bottom of this panel. The main area contains three vertically stacked plots. The top plot, titled 'Neon peaks', shows a series of red and blue vertical lines representing peak positions and heights against a wavelength axis from 540 to 660 nm. The middle plot shows a Gaussian fit (blue line) to a peak (yellow line) on a wavelength axis from 480 to 560 nm. The bottom plot shows a spectrum with a sharp peak at approximately 1000 cm⁻¹, comparing the 'original' (red line) with the 'calibrated' (green line) data on a wavenumber axis from 0 to 2000 cm⁻¹. Three red arrows originate from the right side of the image: one points to the 'Laser Wavelength' dropdown, another points to the 'Peak profile' dropdown, and the third points to the 'prominence' dropdown in the 'Peak finding options' section.

Set Laser wavelength

Set peak profile

Set optimal parameters for peak finding

Save x axis calibration to a file

Calibration curve

Peak profile

Gaussian

Should fit

Lazer zeroing

Pearson4

Should fit

Peak finding options

prominence 3.0

wlen 200

width 1.0

Save calibration model

2 RC2Spectra + Neon 1 RC2Spectra + 1 Si RC2Spectra 2 RC2Spectra

Use button **Save calibration model**

17. Apply previously created x calibration

Use widgets:
x-calibration Load
Load File
x-calibration - Apply

18. Basic workflow for y calibration

Example workflow is available at:

<https://github.com/h2020charisma/oranchada/tree/main/examples>

y calibration widget input connections (channels)

y calibration widget

The screenshot shows the 'Y axis calibration - Orange' software window. The interface includes a menu bar (View, Window, Help), a toolbar with navigation and plot controls, and a control panel on the left. The control panel has the following settings:

- Main Options:**
 - Auto update plot
 - Pass datatable
 - Auto process
- Buttons:** 'Process' (highlighted), 'Plot'
- Plot legend:**
- Y axis calibration:**
 - Select Wavelength: 532
 - Select SRM Certificate: NIST532_SRM2242a

The main plot area displays two spectra. The top plot shows 'Intensity' on the y-axis (0 to 60000) versus wavelength on the x-axis (0 to 4000). It features a blue spectrum with several peaks and a magenta curve representing a fit. The legend identifies the magenta curve as 'NIST532_Probe_3000msx8_1.txt' and the blue curve as 'NIST532_SRM2242a (532nm)'. The bottom plot shows a zoomed-in view of the blue spectrum with a legend entry 'id(spe)=2086029061264'.

19. Using Oranchada together with Spectroscopy widgets

Oranchada widgets could be combined with Spectroscopy widgets

Pass (transfer) data to Spectroscopy widgets

By default Oranchada passes RC2Spectra objects. In order to transfer data to Spectroscopy, check option **Pass datatable**

Connect Data output to Data input

The image shows the Oranchada software interface. On the left, the 'Main Options' panel has the 'Pass datatable' checkbox checked and highlighted with a red box. Below it are 'Process' and 'Plot' buttons, and a 'Load Test Spectra' section with a list of objects (01, 010, 02, 020, 03). The main window displays a Raman spectrum plot with 'Raman shift [cm⁻¹]' on the x-axis (0 to 4000) and intensity on the y-axis (0 to 60000). A legend indicates 'id(spe)=2796106554896'. On the right, the 'Edit Links - Oranchada' dialog box is open, showing connections between 'Load Test Spectra' and 'Spectra' widgets. The 'Data' output of 'Load Test Spectra' is connected to the 'Data' input of 'Spectra'. The 'Pass datatable' checkbox is also checked in this dialog. A red arrow points from the 'Pass datatable' checkbox in the main window to the 'Pass datatable' checkbox in the dialog. Another red arrow points from the 'Data' output of 'Load Test Spectra' to the 'Data' input of 'Spectra' in the dialog. A black arrow points from the 'Data' input of 'Spectra' to the 'Data' checkbox in the dialog.

Transfer data from Spectroscopy to Oranchada

Spectroscopy widget

Use Table to RCSpectra widget

By default, the output channel from Spectroscopy is **Selection**. Change to **Data** output when needed.

